

TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH DIDACTIC GAMES TO PRESCHOOLERS

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Annotation: *The main components of any didactic game are the didactic and game task, game rules and actions, the result and didactic material. In some didactic games, there may be a plot and a role. The goal of the article is to clarify the importance of some didactic game techniques used in teaching FL to preschoolers.*

Key words: *methods, game methods, preschoolers, educational tasks, didactic games, lexical materials, skill, ability, multimedia presentations, role-playing game.*

INTRODUCTION

The game as a means of teaching a foreign language is considered in the research works of K. A. Rodkin, M. F. Stronin, E. I. Negnevitskaya, D. Strange and other scientists and has found wide application in the practice of teaching a foreign language. At an early stage of language learning, game methods and techniques arouse increased interest in children, positive emotions, help to focus on the learning task, which becomes the personal goal of the preschooler. The solution of an educational task in a playful way occurs with less expenditure of the nervous system, requires less volitional effort from the child. The game in the process of communication in a foreign language is always emotionally colored, which contributes to the rapid and lasting assimilation of linguistic, and primarily lexical material.

METHODOLOGY

In the technology of forming lexical skills, the main stages of work on vocabulary are distinguished: familiarization with new material; training; development of skills and abilities to use vocabulary in various types of speech activity, which are a single whole. Familiarization of preschoolers with vocabulary is carried out mainly through non-translating techniques: showing an object, pictures, actions, since most of the lexical units reflect objects and objects of reality.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Training techniques include:

- 1) pronunciation of words, phrases, sentences in audio recording or behind the teacher;
- 2) oral compilation of phrases with a new word;
- 3) the use of a new word in different speech patterns, etc.

At this stage, the primary phonetic training involves imitation exercises, that is, repeated repetition, pronunciation of the word not only in isolation, but also in phrases and sentences. All this contributes to the memorization of a lexical unit, its introduction into memory, that is, the accumulation of a dictionary¹. This type of exercise allows children to master the sound form of lexical units, provides the formation of an approximate pronunciation, that is, one that does not distort the meaning of the word, which is necessary for the act of communication to take place. But repeated repetition of words does not cause much interest in children. In this case, the game can serve as a training exercise. Phonetic development of new words can be carried out in the game "Echo", but by performing the reproduction of the word after the teacher, the children are already playing. For this game, a special attribute is used, a picture that imitates sound, which changes its size. Children pronounce a new word after the teacher three times, each time pronouncing the word quieter and quieter. The games "Optimist and Surprised", "Fast Fun", "Our Turtle Girlfriend", which are held at the training stage,

¹ Rogova G. V., Vereshchagina I. N. Methods of teaching English at the initial stage in a general educational institution: A manual for teachers and students of pedagogical universities - 3rd edition / G. V. Rogova, I. N. Vereshchagina. - M.: Education, 2000. - 232 p.

and later serve as a kind of repetition of the studied material, allow you to influence the emotional sphere of the child and also contribute to memorizing vocabulary.

Performing a training exercise, children pronounce words cheerfully, surprised, quickly, slowly. The game "Visiting Dunno" allows kids to listen to lexical units again, teach them to respond affirmatively or negatively to how Dunno calls animals, toys, color or number of objects, etc. The game "Magic scarf", with which the teacher closes objects on the table, one of which disappears with a raised handkerchief, contributes to the development of attention and memory.

The didactic task of the children is to name the disappeared object in English. In order to support children's activity aimed at mastering lexical units, the teacher must combine traditional means, subject and picture visualization, with innovative ones, which allow stimulating the child's interest and inquisitiveness in learning about the world around them by means of a foreign language. One of these tools is a multimedia presentation. Multimedia presentations (hereinafter referred to as MMPs) are a convenient and effective way of presenting information using computer programs. MMP is a combination of computer animation, graphics, video, music and sound, which are organized into a single environment and hold the attention of a person for the longest time.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main didactic properties of multimedia is the integration of various types of information (text, sound, video, etc.) that affect several human senses, causing an emotional reaction of the student and interactive interaction with students, i.e. involving students in an active learning process, stimulation of their cognitive activity. These two properties distinguish MMP from other learning tools. According to E. S. Polat, these properties determine the didactic functions of MMP¹ as a means of teaching through their purpose, role and place in the educational process: to integrate different types of information in one object, influencing the senses; stimulate the

¹ Chudochina, T. P. Game in teaching preschool children a foreign language / T. P. Chudochina. - Text: direct // Actual issues of modern pedagogy: materials of the III Intern. scientific conf. (Ufa, March 2013). - T. 0. - Ufa: Summer, 2013. - S. 76-78.

cognitive process; interact interactively with students; create conditions as close as possible to reality for the development of learning skills, etc¹. For example, when studying the topic “Animals”, in order to repeat thematic vocabulary, you can use the game “We are Pathfinders”. On one of the slides, you can “search” for animals in the forest by following their tracks, on the other, by listening to their voices, and on the third, after carefully examining the forest, identify the animals that hid behind the bushes, behind the flowers, behind the trees, where you can only see the ear, tail or paw.

When children have a good command of lexical units, know their meaning, pronounce them correctly, use them in sentences, and are able to combine them with previously studied vocabulary, for example, adjectives denoting color, size, communication exercises can be used. The purpose of such exercises is to describe, tell, question, etc. These exercises can also be carried out in the form of a role-playing game that has a clearly defined didactic structure. The structural components of role play are the roles that children take on; game actions and deeds through which they realize their roles; game use of objects; real relationships between playing children (remarks, remarks that regulate the game).

Role-playing as a whole and its structural components have different meanings for children and the teacher. In the process of playing, children, first of all, are guided by the enjoyment, and not by the significance of the result of the game. For teacher, the structural components of a teaching role-playing game are:

- 1) gaming, practical, educational and developmental goals;
- 2) the content of the role-playing game, which is based mainly on the educational material of the current conversational topic and which acquires a certain plot organization and development;
- 3) a set of social and interpersonal roles through which children realize a significant part of the content of a particular role-playing game;

¹ Bukharina M. Yu. Multimedia: from street shows to teaching aids / M. Yu. Bukharina // Foreign languages at school. - 2009. - No. 5.

4) communicative and linguodidactic conditions, i.e., first of all, the educational and communicative situation created by the children themselves under the guidance of a teacher;

5) props - any items that are somehow included in the role-playing game and acquire a symbolic, communicating meaning.

Communicative conditions are not only the creation of an educational and communicative situation, but the creation of a favorable psychological climate, an atmosphere that predisposes children to interpersonal interaction, showing interest and creative initiative throughout the game¹. An example is the role-playing game "We are going to the zoo", in which the children are pedestrians at the beginning. Walking along the "street", they sing a song: We go, go, go, We go to the Zoo. We go, go, go I and you! Obeying the rules of the road, they cross the street on a zebra, naming the colors of the traffic light and reading the poem "The traffic light". In the "zoo", which is modeled with the help of MMP, each child becomes a guide, names the animal, describes its color, size, names the actions that the animal performs, expresses its attitude towards the animal. Visitors to the zoo, being polite, thank each guide. After the tour, the teacher discusses with the children their trip to the zoo, asks about the number of animals, what kind of animals they are, wild or domestic, reminds us that we must take care and take care of animals, and, being on the street, follow the rules for pedestrians.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the use of games in the process of teaching preschoolers a foreign language enhances the learning effect, increases their motivation to learn the language in an exciting interactive way, and contributes to the development of speech skills and abilities.

¹ Filatov V. M., Filatova G. E. Theory and practice of early teaching foreign languages. Textbook for pedagogical colleges, language pedagogical universities. - Rostov N / D: Anion, 1999. - 384 p.

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